

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF GERMAN - UZBEKIAN LANGUAGES (BASED ON THE WOLF OF THE DESERT BY HERMANN HESSE)

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of homonymy, which is described by the perfect or partial matching of linguistic units in the language, is one of the characteristics shared by the Uzbek and German languages. The primary unit of a language's vocabulary and the focus of lexicology study is the word. current linguistics word descriptions. the primary word symbols in contemporary German. The definition of the word according to conventional logic and linguistics. The word's lexical meaning and its several forms. The semantic structure of the word. Polysemy as a typical phenomenon in modern German. In this article, the comparative typology of German-Uzbek mants based on Hermann Hesse's desert wolf is discussed.

According to the content plan, the science of typology compares and summarizes various hierarchical language system units and classifies them into normal typology and semantic typology. The sections of the typology are as follows, based on how the language levels interact:

- phonological and phonetic typology
- morphological typology
- syntactic typology
- lexical typology.

Along with the aforementioned, sociolinguistic, graphic, and methodological typologies are also present. The Greek words "tipos" - type, type, image, shape, sign - and "logos" - word, science - are combined to form the word typology. Nowadays, typology is common across all academic areas. According to this viewpoint, the notion of linguistic typology belongs to the macrocategory. According to the relationship between objects or events and the act of description, typology is separated into two categories:

- (i) linguistic typology
- (ii) non-linguistic typology.

Linguistic typology studies the comparison of language systems with each other, the generalization of language laws and categories, and their typological classification. This type of linguistic typology is called pure linguistic typology and is contrasted with extra-linguistic

typology. Extra-linguistic typology compares and contrasts language with other systems close to this language, for example, semiotic communication and other sign systems. The semiotic system includes human language, animal language, machine language system, and others.

The primary method for expanding the vocabulary of the modern German language is word creation. the connection between grammar and word production. the core of word production as seen from a lexicological perspective. Modern German word formation techniques and their output. In contemporary German, phrasing serves as an effective means of word creation. combinations of words, compound words with qualifiers, and complex compound words. Word formation and its types: affixal and explicit word formation (suffixation and prefixation) and word formation without affixes (transformation and conversion). The uniqueness of complex word formation methods.

One of the features common to the Uzbek and German languages is the phenomenon of homonymy, which is explained by the complete or partial correspondence of linguistic units in the language (full pure) or functional homonyms). There are several reasons for the formation of homonymic features in languages:

- a). By accidental phonetic similarity: Saite-Seite, Weise-Waise,
- b). As a result of the conversion: brennen-das Brennen, leben – das Leben,
- c). Through adjectives: Montage some Mondays, Montage(montage),
- d). Through the shift of semantic meaning in words: Fuss (foot) - Fuss (foot of the mountain).

Instead of simplifying your heart and confining your universe, Hermann Hesse suggests in *The Wolf of the Desert* that you now broaden it in order to reach the afterlife and the eternal world. "The path to God leads not in the way of a wolf or a child, but in the way of repentance and the way of becoming a man", said the apostle Paul. In Genesis, there is no virginity, simplicity, innocence, or honesty. Even the seemingly most basic created organisms are corruptible and prone to sin.

In Hermann Hesse's "Wolf of the Desert", as a person lives in the world of existence, sometimes pulling the thread of life tightly, sometimes loosely, the thought that flashes in the moment of "realization" causes either light or darkness. However, the person who sees the gap will go to the cliff willingly. The strong psyche of Hesse's characters infects the reader to such an extent that the carelessness and disappointment joins your character. In fact, the writer forms the complexities of the hero's psyche in the process of internal experiences and the brutal struggle of the mind, in which the resulting duality (there may be two or more) forms a single character: Man and Animal.

The battle between the wolf and the human that inhabit Harry, the desert wolf's hero, has been settled in such a way that one prepares the way for the advent of the other. Harry lives in a shell as a result of two opposing images that separate him from other people and alienate him from life's necessities. Even the most intellectual and educated individual frequently views the world and himself through the lenses of formulas that are invariably too simple, simplistic, and in other ways misleading.

Although in Eastern literature, the process of returning to one's identity, understanding, knowing the "I" is accompanied by mental suffering, in the stage of perfection, the feeling of "I" in the "I" gives comfort to a person and further strengthens life activity. In the West,

returning to the "I", the perfect solution for a person staring at the gaping void at the end of consciousness, is suicide. In Harry's life, the presence of death at every step makes it possible to live. Perhaps the writer wanted to show the limit of possibility and impossibility, using the context effectively. To "live as if the world is not the world", you should take a look at the analysis of your body, which deviates from the rules-norms of life.

Harry's analysis process was sparked when he unintentionally came into possession of a completed book. Observing even seemingly straightforward procedures in intricate detail sparked a critical appraisal of his predicament that resulted in a mental breakdown, impotence, and disappointment. Goes However, "there is no path that leads either to childhood or to wolfishness".

No matter how far we go from the seemingly small aspects of life, then there may be a chance, an unbroken thread between life and death. Already, the thread held by Harry leads to an easy life. For Harry, who is tired of harsh, ruthless self-examination, dancing, girls, parties, love are the beginning of this path, a great solution to distract from unnecessary thoughts! Since time immemorial, man has preferred to reward himself rather than beat himself up.

Hermann Hesse is an autobiographical work of the writer, I don't know to what extent Hesse found a life opportunity for himself in this event, but it is commendable that Harry put an unlimited amount of desire to live in his heart! When you see thousands of images hidden behind your unconscious desires in your heart, the "I" disappears in the moment of neglect. If you want to go back, Rumi is a good treatment for medicine, and Hesse for analysis.

There are linguistic and extralinguistic explanations for word meaning changes. The three basic ways that a word's meaning can change are through expanding, narrowing, or strengthening it. The most common ways that word meanings are transferred and their quirks. Metonymy and metaphor. Metaphoric and metonymic meaning can alter in various ways. Synesthesia, synecdoche, exaggeration, euphemism, hyperbola, and litota. Relationships between metaphors and metonyms as a form of systematic polysemy. methods for creating new word meanings.

In linguistics, typology is a branch of linguistics that identifies and summarizes the important features of the structure of the language in general, based on the study of the construction of some derived languages and their comprehensive comparison. Typological methods are aimed at identifying similarities and differences based on the phonology, morphology, syntax and lexis of different regional languages, defining linguistic universals, as well as types of languages - generalized, perfect concepts of the nature of language construction.

In conclusion, a general typology is linguistic typology, which incorporates all typological techniques. The outcomes produced by certain typological techniques are summarized by general typology. From a generic typological perspective, all language systems in the world are various panchronic versions of a single structure. For this reason, typology researches the connections between various components of general rules and linguistic structures. General typology establishes language universes, defines the typological laws of all languages, and deduces universal laws from some languages to apply to other languages.

References:

1. Hermann Hesse. "Desert wolf", translator Mirzaali Akbarov, 2015.
2. <https://kitobkhon.com/oz/kitob/chol-borisi>
3. Rahmatullaev Sh. Explanatory dictionary of homonyms of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1984.
4. Abjalova M. Database of homonyms in the Uzbek language. 2020.
5. Lutfullayeva D., Davlatova R., Tojiboyev B. Associative dictionary of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: 2019.
6. Mirtojiev M. Phonetics of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: 2013.
7. Jamolkhanov H. Contemporary Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent: 2013.